

Cholecystoduodenal Fistula: Rare Complication of Gallstone Disease and Its Management

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Cholecystoduodenal fistula (CDF) is an abnormal connection between the gallbladder and the duodenum “blue loop”, occurring in approximately 1% of patients with gallstone disease. It primarily affects elderly individuals with long-standing cholelithiasis and recurrent cholecystitis. Women are more commonly affected due to the higher prevalence of gallstone disease. CDF typically develops over time as large gallstones erode through the gallbladder wall into the duodenum. Although uncommon, it can lead to serious complications like gallstone ileus or biliary obstruction. Advances in imaging, such as CT and MRCP, have improved detection rates. Surgical management is the definitive treatment for this pathological condition. The preferred approach is cholecystectomy with fistula closure, either through an open or laparoscopic procedure.

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